

IMPROVEMENT OF COMBINED SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CHRONIC HEMORRHOIDS CONCURRENT WITH CHRONIC ANAL FISSURE: OUTCOMES OF A MODIFIED HEMORRHOIDECTOMY TECHNIQUE

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Abstract

The coexistence of chronic hemorrhoids and chronic anal fissure represents one of the most challenging combined anorectal conditions encountered in coloproctological practice. Despite the availability of various surgical techniques, no single standardized approach has been established that consistently minimizes postoperative morbidity and long-term recurrence in patients with concurrent stage III–IV hemorrhoids and anal fissure. This prospective comparative study was conducted at the Proctology Department of Samarkand State Medical University Clinic and the "Doctor O" Clinic between 2021 and 2025, enrolling 132 patients with concurrent stage III–IV chronic hemorrhoids and chronic anal fissure. Patients were divided into two groups: the control group (n = 65) underwent closed hemorrhoidectomy (Milligan–Morgan modification II), open fissurectomy, and lateral subcutaneous sphincterotomy; the study group (n = 67) underwent a novel modified combined procedure comprising hemorrhoidectomy with maximum preservation of the anal canal mucosa, fissurectomy with transverse wound closure, and circular excision of external hemorrhoidal nodes. The two groups were comparable in terms of sex, age distribution, and clinical characteristics. The primary outcomes assessed included early postoperative complications, local anal canal temperature (used as a proxy for wound inflammation on days 3, 5, and 7), hospital length of stay, disability duration, and long-term outcomes at 6 months to 3 years.

In the control group, severe pain syndrome was observed in 46 (71.5%) patients on the first postoperative day, compared with 28 (41.5%) patients in the study group ($P < 0.001$). Postoperative hemorrhage from the vascular pedicle stump occurred in 2 (3.1%) control group patients, whereas no such complication was recorded in the study group. Minor bleeding during the first wound dressing was observed in 19 (31.0%) control group patients versus 6 (8.9%) in the study group ($P < 0.001$). Difficulty with the first defecation was reported in 18 (28.5%) control group patients compared with 7 (10.4%) in the study group ($P < 0.001$). Acute postoperative paraproctitis developed in 1 (1.5%) control group patient, with no such cases in the study group. Reflex urinary retention occurred in 5 (7.7%) and 2 (2.9%) patients in the control and study groups, respectively. Mean anal canal temperature on postoperative days 3, 5, and 7 was $37.4 \pm 0.3^\circ\text{C}$, $37.8 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$, and $37.3 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ in the control group, compared with $37.3 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$, $37.5 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, and $37.2 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ in the study group, reflecting a lower degree of local wound inflammation in the modified technique cohort.

Mean hospital length of stay was 9.6 ± 1.1 bed-days in the control group and 8.2 ± 0.4 bed-days in the study group ($P < 0.05$). Mean disability duration was 28.2 ± 1.4 days and 26.4 ± 1.2 days, respectively. Long-term follow-up data, available for 38 (58.4%) control group and 39 (57.8%) study group patients, demonstrated that anal sphincter insufficiency developed in 6 (9.2%) versus 1 (2.6%) patients, anal canal stricture in 3 (7.8%) versus 1 (2.6%), minor pain at

defecation in 8 (21.1%) versus 2 (5.2%), minor rectal bleeding in 5 (13.1%) versus 2 (5.2%), and anal fissure recurrence in 4 (10.5%) versus 0 patients, in the control and study groups, respectively.

These findings demonstrate that the proposed modified combined surgical technique — incorporating fissurectomy with transverse wound closure and circular excision of external hemorrhoidal nodes with preservation of the anoderm — significantly reduces both early and late postoperative complication rates. The complete elimination of anal fissure recurrence in the study group is particularly noteworthy. The technique is technically straightforward and reproducible in specialized surgical settings. The results support the wider adoption of this approach in the management of stage III–IV chronic hemorrhoids concurrent with chronic anal fissure.

Keywords: chronic hemorrhoids, chronic anal fissure, hemorrhoidectomy, fissurectomy, transverse wound closure, postoperative complications, anal sphincter insufficiency, anal canal stricture, combined anorectal surgery.

